

THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE CONCEPT OF FOREGROUNDING

Bukharbayeva Kamola

Master. Department of Linguistics

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Annotation: *The foregrounding a technique that reveals itself rather than hides itself. He finds the most obvious examples of foregrounding in the works of Stern, Joyce, Rimbaud, Faulkner and Beckett, and to explain the essence of estrangement he uses Beckett's apology for Joyce's artistic method.*

Keywords: *foregrounding, linguistics, cohesion, convergence, cognitive science, external imagery, metaphor.*

INTRODUCTION

The foregrounding, according to Arnold, covers different types (subtypes) of contextual ordering: cohesion, convergence, deceived expectation, outstanding feature, strong position, etc. The foregrounding a technique that reveals itself rather than hides itself. He finds the most obvious examples of foregrounding in the works of Stern, Joyce, Rimbaud, Faulkner and Beckett, and to explain the essence of estrangement he uses Beckett's apology for Joyce's artistic method¹. When it is recalled that to critics who, while rejecting Joyce's strange method, caustically remarked that Joyce writes books "not in English" (cf. not only to read, but also to watch and listen. Joyce's writing is not about something, it is "his writing is not about something, it is that something itself"². The drafts of legendary novels provide us with a unique opportunity to trace

¹ file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/Foregrounding_by_Schirova2015.pdf

² Cuddon J. A. The Penguin Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory. Third Ed. L., 1992.

Joyce's "step-by-step change" of the text "from the norm to the author's neoplasm"¹. Once again confirming the validity of R. Jakobson's words about the regularity of the union of linguistics and literary criticism, the foregrounding forms an important research problem in both sciences. So, in the description of I.V. Arnold, who has long become a classic for a Russian linguist, the foregrounding is interpreted "as a unit of the textual level, built on top of the level of stylistic devices²; a formal technique that makes the statement more meaningful.

METHODOLOGY

All of them do not exclude each other, but can occur separately and together, spreading to the entire text or to its individual parts. Literary contexts for the use of the concept of foregrounding are no less diverse. The term is used to: describe the mimetic mode of artistic creation in Renaissance literature; stylistic experiment in modernist literature; differences between postcolonial literature and the literature of the imperialist center, etc³. Despite a rather long history of comprehension in the humanities, the concept of foregrounding is still being actively discussed today, and its new interpretations naturally take into account the principles of the cognitive scientific paradigm. Refinement of the principles of foregrounding based on the approaches of cognitive science makes it possible to describe the basic principles of text organization based on the universal mechanisms of attention distribution and language methods of implementation.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Cognitive science characterizes the foregrounding as a concept and proceeds from the special significance of the psychological aspects of this phenomenon, the role it plays in the processes of text generation and text perception. The foregrounding is correlated with "the importance of placing the language form in the foreground, which

¹ Sergaeva Yu.V. *Linguo-cognitive mechanisms of creative search (on the basis of drafts by J. Joyce)* // Bulletin of the Leningrad State University. un-ta im. A.S. Pushkin. Series Philology No. 4 (18) St. Petersburg, Publishing House of Leningrad State University

² Arnold I.V. *Semantics. Stylistics. Intertextuality*. SPb., 1999. Gavranek B. *Tasks of the literary language and its culture* // Prague Linguistic Circle. M., 1967. S. 338–378.

³ Douthwaite J. *Towards a Linguistic Theory of Foregrounding* Torino, 2000.

acts as a search stimulus, or a key in the processes of linguistic information processing (Kubryakova, Demyankov, Pankrats, Luzina, 1996). L.G. Luzina notes the connection between the psychological reality of the foregrounding concept and surprise, surprise, and increased attention, which, in her opinion, distinguish the foregrounding from another concept that is similar in content - emphasis materiality V.Z. Demyankov, who analyzes the same set of concepts in detail, writes that, although they receive ambiguous interpretations, they are within the unified framework of cognitive theories, "accepting that he himself is at the center of the inner world of each person," and perceiving the world as an intersubjective reality. "The logically coherent system of 'relevance'" by which a person is guided in life determines both what he assumes, and his motivation, and his action in the social world "¹

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As they can be seen, the idea of foregrounding is productively used to analyze and explain the mechanisms of generation and actualization of textual meanings. The hierarchy of textual significances established with the help of extension allows one to see the connections between the textual whole and its individual parts, to highlight the main thing against the background of the secondary. The ability of a text element to be put forward is usually associated with a wide range of artistic means that are perceived as forms of deviation from the usual use of language: repetition, metaphor, unusual syntactic organization of the text, pun, alliteration, etc. In the broadest sense, poetic language itself is sometimes recognized as deautomatized. It is justified to note, however, that the aesthetic significance of the elements of a literary text is not limited to external imagery, and the absence of metaphorical images rich in associations in the text does not indicate its stylistic poverty.

¹ Kubryakova E.S., Demyankov V.Z., Pankrats Yu.G., Luzina L.G. A short dictionary of cognitive terms. M., 1996. Literary encyclopedia of terms and concepts. Ed. Nikolyukina N.M., M., 2001.

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